

Appendix A

IR spectra are shown in Fig. S1 of appendix A, the absorption frequencies are positive (there are no imaginary frequencies), indicating that the obtained structures are geometrically stable.

Fig. S1 Calculated infrared (IR) spectra of Gp and its based substances using M06-2X/LANL2DZ level of theory in a gaseous phase.

Appendix B

For Gp and its variants, the electronic density of states (DOS) is displayed in Fig. S2

Fig. S2 Density of states of Gp) and its derivatives Gp-CH₃, Gp-COOH, Gp-CN, Gp-NO₂, and Gp-SOH.